

DYNAMICS OF CROPPING PATTERN IN PAITHAN LEFT BANK CANAL COMMAND OF JAYAKWADI IRRIGATION PROJECT IN MARATHWADA REGION OF MAHARASHTRA

Kamble S. H., Guledagudda S. S., and Kulkarni G. N.

Department of Agricultural Economics, College of Agriculture, Dharwad-580005, Karnataka.

kamblesh77@gmail.com

(MS Received: 21.11.2023; MS Revised:27.12.2023; MS Accepted:28.12.2023)

MS 3119 (RESEARCH PAPER IN SOIL SCIENCE AND AGRICULTURAL CHEMISTRY,)

Abstract

The results of the study revealed that, during kharif season, perennial crops, soybean and sugarcane were the most stable crops in PLBC command area. About 41.3 per cent area under cotton is shifted to soybean in last 20 years. Similarly, area under sorghum, pearl millet and cotton was stable up to 71.9 per cent, 54.7 per cent and 54.5 per cent, respectively. During rabi season, it was observed that, sugarcane, perennial crops and wheat were the most stable crops in command area, with the retention probability of 97.4 per cent, 88.1 per cent and 84.7 per cent, respectively. Whereas, during summer season, area under sugarcane and perennial crops was more stable. Thus, from this analysis it is concluded that, due to availability of irrigation water, cash crops like sugarcane is prominently grown in the command area. Also, during kharif season area under cotton crop is diverted to soybean crop, because of more profitability of soybean over cotton.

Key words- kharif season, perennial crops, PLBC command area.

Introduction

Cropping pattern is a dynamic concept that changes over time and space. It is the proportion of land under various crops at any given time. Rainfall, climate, soil type, technology, and farmers' socio-economic conditions are some of the major factors affects the cropping pattern of a region. Besides, these factors, availability of the irrigation facilities is also another factors which play major role in determining the cropping pattern. On the basis of availability of the irrigation resources, crops to be grown are being selected by the farmers, i.e. there is strong relation between irrigation and the cropping pattern of a region (Bharatharathna *et al.*, 2019). Keeping in view the importance of irrigation in determining the cropping pattern of a region, dynamics of cropping pattern in Paithan Left Bank Canal (PLBC) command of Jayakwadi Irrigation Project were studied. Jayakwadi Dam was built to cater to multiple needs of the Marathwada region of the state of Maharashtra and till today, it is serving its various purposes. This multipurpose project not only provides water for irrigation in the drought-prone areas of the region like Aurangabad, Ahmednagar, Beed, Jalna, and Parbhani, but also for drinking, industrial usage, and electricity generation. With its extensive canal system, the dam provides irrigation to approximately 237,452 hectares of cultivable land.

Methodology

For the present study past 20 years' time series data (2000-01 to 2020-21) regarding cropping pattern in command area were collected from the various reports of Irrigation Department and analyzed through first order Markov chain analysis. The dynamics of cropping pattern was studied in three different season's viz., kharif, rabi and summer with the help of Transitional Probability Matrix (TPM).

Markov Chain Analysis

Markov chain analysis was employed to diagnose the shift in the area among the different crops over the period of time in command area. It is an application of dynamic programming to the solution of a stochastic decision process that can be described by a finite number of states to study the changes in the cropping pattern (Dayakar, 2005).

The Markov Probability

A stochastic process can analyze a set of trials or experiments probabilistically. For a stochastic process, it is assumed that the movements (transitions) of objects from one state (possible outcome) to another are governed by a probabilistic mechanism. A finite Markov process is a stochastic process whereby the outcome of a given trial 't' (t = 1, 2, ..., T) depends only on the outcome of a preceding trial (t-1) and this dependence is the same at all stages of the sequence of trials (Lee *et al.*, 1965). Consistent with this definition, let the S_i represent i^{th} state or possible outcomes; $i = 1, 2, \dots, r$, W_{it} represent the probability that state S_i occurs on trial t or proportion observed in trial 't', in alternative outcome state I of a multinomial population based on sample size n, i.e. $P_r(S_{it})$. P_{ij} represent the transitional probability which denotes the probability

that if for any time 't' the process is in stable S_i , it moves on next trial state S_j ,

$$\text{i.e. } P_r(S_j, t + 1 / S_{it}) = P_{ij}$$

$P_r = (P_{ij})$ represent transitional probability matrix which denotes transitional probability for every pair of states (i, j = 1, 2, 3, ..., r) and has the following properties;

$$0 \leq P_{ij} \leq 1 \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Given this set of notations and definitions for a first order Markov chain, the probability of particular sequence S_i on trial t and S_j on trial t+1 may be represented by

$$\sum_{j=1}^n P_{ij} = 1 \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

$$P_r(S_{it}, S_{i+1}) = P_r(S_{it}) P_r(S_{i+1}/S_{it}) = W_{it} P_{ij} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

And the probability of being in state j at trial t+1 may be represented by

$$P_r(S_{i(t-1)}) = \sum_i W_{it} P_j \text{ or } W_{j(t+1)} = \sum_i W_{it} P_{ij} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

The data for study are the proportion of area under crops. The proportion changes from year to year as a result of factors like weather, technology, price and institutional changes etc. it is reasonable to assume that the combined influence of these individually systematic forces approximates to a stochastic process and propensity of farmers to move from one crop to another differs according to the crop state involved. The process of cropping pattern change may be described in form of matrix P of first order transition probabilities. The element P_{ij} indicates the probability of a crop i in one period will move to crop state j during the following period. The diagonal element P_{ij} measures the probability that the proportion share i^{th} category of crop will be retained (Ardesna and Shiyani, 2013).

Estimation of Transitional Probability Matrix (TPM)

Equation (4) can be used as a basis for specifying the statistical model for estimating transitional probabilities. If errors are incorporated in equation (4), it becomes,

$$W_{it} = \sum_i W_{it} W_i, t-1 P_{ij} + U_{it} \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

or in matrix form it can be written as,

$$Y_j = X_i P_j + U_j \dots \dots \dots (6)$$

Where,

$Y_j = (T \times 1)$ vectors of observations reflecting the proportions in cropping pattern j in time t,

$X_j = (T \times r)$ matrix of realized values of the proportions in cropping pattern in time t-1,

$P_j = (r \times 1)$ vectors of unknown transition parameters to be estimated and

$U_j =$ vectors of random disturbances.

Results and Discussion

The results of Markov chain analysis to find out changes in the direction of different crops in PLBC command were presented in the form of a transition probability matrix. As the diagonal elements approach zero, the crops become less and less stable and as they

approach one, implies that they become more and more stable over a period of time. In the transition probability matrix rows showed the previous period acreage of the corresponding crop lost to the other crops in the current period and columns indicate area gained from the other crops (Ramya Lakshmi and Bhavani Devi (2012); Rajini Devi et al.(2019)).

Table 1 indicates Transitional Probability Matrix for shift in cropping pattern in PLBC during *kharif* season. It is observed from the table that, among all the crops, perennial crops has the highest retention probability with 95.7 per cent followed by soybean and sugarcane. The retention probability of area under soybean and sugarcane was 94.5 per cent and 91.5 per cent, respectively. Soybean lost its minor share of 5.5 per cent to sugarcane and gained 41.3 per cent area from cotton and 5.2 per cent from sugarcane crops. Similarly, sugarcane lost its 5.2 per cent area to soybean and 3.3 per cent to sorghum and gained major share of 31.6 per cent from pearl millet and 5.5 per cent and 4.2 per cent from soybean and cotton, respectively.

The retention probability of previous year area under cotton, pearl millet and sorghum was 54.5 per cent, 54.7 per cent and 71.9 per cent, respectively. Cotton has lost its 41.3 per cent area to soybean and 4.2 per cent to sugarcane, while gained 4.7 per cent and 9.2 per cent area from pearl millet and sorghum, respectively. Pearl millet lost 31.6 per cent of its area to sugarcane, 4.7 per cent to cotton and 9 per cent to sorghum; whereas gained 18.3 per cent area from sorghum. In case of sorghum, it is observed that, sorghum has retained 71.9 per cent of its previous years area by losing 18.3 per cent to pearl millet, 9.2 per cent to cotton and gaining 3.3 per cent area from sugarcane, 9.0 per cent from pearl millet and 4.3 per cent from perennial crops. It is concluded from the analysis that, perennial crops, soybean and sugarcane crops were the most stable crops in the command area. Due to availability of the irrigation water cash crops like sugarcane were mostly preferred by the farmers, whereas perennial crops like sweet orange were prominent due to suitable climatic conditions. But, area under cash crops like cotton was reducing, and it was gained by soybean crop. Because, soybean was more profitable crop than cotton, its duration is also less than cotton and it fetched very good price than cotton. Similarly, expenses on plant protection chemicals in soybean crops were less than cotton crops. Therefore, farmers were diverted from cotton to soybean. The previous year's area under sorghum and pearl millet was retained with 71.9 and 54.7 per cent. Since, these crops are the staple food of the region, and these crops are the important source of fodder to the dairy enterprise in the region. These results were similar to the results obtained by Reddy, *et al* (2022) wherein they found that, cash crop like cotton was more stable in Krishna zone of AP. Manvar and Nagpure (2017), also found that area of other minor crops were diverted to cotton and soybean in Wardha district of Maharashtra.

Transitional Probability Matrix for shift in cropping pattern in PLBC during *rabi* season is shown in Table 2. Among all the crops in *rabi* season sugarcane has retained its share in previous years area to the extent of 97.4 per cent probability. Sugarcane has lost 2.6 per cent of its area to sunflower crop. Wheat has retained 84.7 per cent of its previous year's area by losing 15.3 per cent area to gram and retaining 29.6 per cent and 18.7 per cent area from cotton and gram crops, respectively. In case of gram crop, it has been observed that gram has retained 79.8 per cent of its previous year's area and lost 18.7 per cent and 1.5 per cent area to wheat and sorghum crops. Sorghum retained 68.4 per cent of its previous year's area by losing 21.6 per cent and 10 per cent area to sunflower and perennial crops while gained 10 per cent and 1.5 per cent area from sunflower and gram crops. Cotton retained 49.4 percent of its previous year's area by losing 29.6 per cent and 21 per cent area to wheat and gram crops; whereas gained 24.5 per cent area from sunflower. The retention probability of area under sunflower crop was 39.6 per cent which loosed 25.9 percent, 10 per cent and 24.5 per cent area to gram, sorghum and cotton crops and gained about 21.6 per cent and 2.6 per cent area from sorghum and sugarcane crops. Perennial crops had retain 88.10 per cent of its

previous area by losing 11.9 per cent area to gram and gaining 10 per cent area from sorghum crops. This analysis also indicated that, during *rabi* season also, sugarcane, perennials, wheat and gram were the most stable crops. Since, sugarcane and perennial fruit crops like sweet lime are the cash crops of the region which requires irrigation and wheat is staple food and gram is best suitable crop in *rabi* season in the Marathwada region. These findings are similar to the findings of Rangegowda and Umesh (2017) who analysed the shifts in cropping pattern between major agricultural and horticultural crops in hilly zone of Karnataka and concluded that shift in crop area found from traditionally grown, less remunerative crop to more remunerative horticultural crops.

Table 3 presents Transitional Probability Matrix for shift in cropping pattern in PLBC during summer season. It is observed from table that among all summer season crops sugarcane retained 90.5 per cent of its previous year's area by losing 9.5 per cent area to groundnut and by gaining 25.3 per cent, 4 per cent and 39.4 per cent area from groundnut, sorghum and sunflower crops, respectively. Retention probability of summer groundnut was 64.7 per cent. Groundnut loosed 25.3 per cent area to sugarcane, and 10 per cent area to sunflower, whereas gained 27.9 per cent area from sorghum and 9.5 per cent area from sugarcane. Similarly, sorghum retained 52.1 per cent share of its previous years' area by gaining 20.5 per cent and 10.8 per cent area from sunflower and perennial crops; whereas it loosed 27.9 per cent and 16 per cent area to groundnut and sunflower, respectively. Retention probability of sunflower crop was 40.1 per cent by losing 39.4 per cent and 20.5 per cent area to sugarcane and sorghum, respectively, and by gaining 10 per cent and 16 per cent area from groundnut and sorghum, respectively. Perennial crops retained with 89.2 per cent probability by losing 10.8 per cent area to sorghum crop. Thus, in summer season also, sugarcane and perennial crops were the most stable crops. Also, the area under groundnut, sorghum and sunflower were also stable to the extent of 64.7 per cent, 52.10 and 40.10 per cent, respectively. Pujari and Poddar (2016), also reported that, in command area under different crops was diverted to commercial crops.

References

1. **Ardeshta N J and Shiyani R L, 2013**, Dynamics of Cropping Pattern in Gujarat State: A Markov Chain Approach. *Asian Academic Research Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 1(9) - 56-66.
2. **Bharatharathna A, Prasanna N and Natarajamurthy P, 2019**, Analysis of Role of Irrigation in Cropping Pattern in Salem District, *Indian Journal of Economics and Business*, 18(2): 583-589
3. **Dayakar Rao and Shahid Parwez, 2005**, Dynamics of Cropping Pattern in Sorghum growing States of India. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 60(4): 644-659.
4. **Manwar M K and Nagpure S C, 2017**, Structural changes in cropping pattern. *International Journal of Science, Environment and Technology*, 6(5): 2885-2892.
5. **Pujari V Y and Poddar R S, 2016**, Impact of JSYS tank irrigation on farm economy - A case study of Vijayapura district. *Journal of Farm Science*, 29 (1): 128-130.
6. **Rajini Devi, D.A., Uma Reddy, R., Madavi, B., Ravi, P. and Sadvi, P. 2019**. Dynamics of Cropping Pattern in Karimnagar District of Telangana – A Markov Chain Approach. *Asian Journal of Agricultural Extension, Economics & Sociology*, 37(4): 1-5.
7. **Ramya Lakshmi, S.B. and Bhavani Devi, I. 2012**. Crop Shifts in Coastal Region of Andhra Pradesh: A Markov Chain Approach. *Agricultural Situation in India*, 69(7): 363-368.
8. **Rangegowda R and Umesh K B, 2017**, Dynamics of agri-horti crops in hilly zone of Karnataka: An economic analysis. *Mysore Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 51(2): 216-222.

9. Reddy R G, Reddy C M, Pravallika K and Gita Meher,
2022. Dynamics of cropping pattern in Krishna zone of

Andhara Pradesh – Markov Chain Approach. *Journal of Research, ANGRAU*, 50 (1): 104-115.

Table 1. Transitional Probability Matrix for shift in cropping pattern in PLBC during *kharif* season

Crop	Cotton	Soybean	Sugarcane	Pearl millet	Sorghum	Perennials
Cotton	0.545	0.413	0.042	0.000	0.000	0.000
Soybean	0.000	0.945	0.055	0.000	0.000	0.000
Sugarcane	0.000	0.052	0.915	0.000	0.033	0.000
Pearl millet	0.047	0.000	0.316	0.547	0.090	0.000
Sorghum	0.092	0.000	0.006	0.183	0.719	0.000
Perennials	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.043	0.957

Table 2. Transitional Probability Matrix for shift in cropping pattern in PLBC during *rabi* season

Crop	Wheat	Gram	Sorghum	Cotton	Sugarcane	Sunflower	Perennials
Wheat	0.847	0.153	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Gram	0.187	0.798	0.015	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Sorghum	0.000	0.000	0.684	0.000	0.000	0.216	0.100
Cotton	0.296	0.210	0.000	0.494	0.000	0.000	0.000
Sugarcane	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.974	0.026	0.000
Sunflower	0.000	0.259	0.100	0.245	0.000	0.396	0.000
Perennials	0.000	0.119	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.881

Table 3. Transitional Probability Matrix for shift in cropping pattern in PLBC during summer season

Crop	Sugarcane	Groundnut	Sorghum	Sunflower	Perennials
Sugarcane	0.905	0.095	0.000	0.000	0.000
Groundnut	0.253	0.647	0.000	0.100	0.000
Sorghum	0.040	0.279	0.521	0.160	0.000
Sunflower	0.394	0.000	0.205	0.401	0.000
Perennials	0.000	0.000	0.108	0.000	0.892